

Assessment of Patients' Knowledge and Awareness of Referral System Policies in Federal and State Tertiary Healthcare Facilities in Bayelsa State

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Abstract

This study evaluates patients' knowledge of referral policies at federal and state tertiary healthcare facilities in Bayelsa State, focusing on their understanding of the referral process and awareness of existing policies. This cross-sectional study focused on new clients at the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, and NDUTH in Bayelsa State. It employed a self-designed five-point Likert scale survey. A sample of 276 was calculated using the Cochran formula, with accidental sampling. Data were analysed using frequency tables and percentages. The study revealed that 63.4% of respondents lacked awareness of the healthcare referral system. Approximately half believed referral systems waste time and obstruct access, and the same proportion felt the system does not promote close relationships across healthcare levels. Slightly over 51% disagreed that the system enhances transparency and efficiency. Additionally, 33.7% were uncertain whether a structured policy exists, while 55.4% thought the referral system is inactive in their facility. Patients generally lack awareness of the healthcare referral system, policies, and guidelines. The system does not foster strong links between healthcare levels. Education for patients and the public is essential, and the government should improve facilities and clarify policies to boost access and efficiency.

Keywords: Patients, Knowledge, Awareness, Referral System, Policies, Healthcare Facilities

Introduction

A healthcare referral system is vital for any healthcare system to provide consistent, prompt, and high-quality care. In Nigeria, the referral system ensures that patients transition from basic to specialist healthcare based on the severity of their condition (Federal Ministry of Health [FMOH], 2016). The effectiveness of the system depends on both healthcare professionals and patients being aware of how the referral system works (Adewoyin & Ogunfowokan, 2019). When patients understand referrals, they are more likely to follow them, seek care at suitable facilities, and achieve better outcomes (Olaoye et al., 2021).

In Bayelsa State, tertiary healthcare centres such as the Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Yenagoa, and the Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital (NDUTH), Okolobiri, receive many referrals from smaller facilities. Although referral guidelines exist, many patients bypass primary and secondary care and go directly to these hospitals without proper referrals. This raises questions about how well patients understand the referral system and why they behave as they do. It is important to find out what patients in Bayelsa State know and understand about referral policies. Doing so will improve the referral process and result in better outcomes in tertiary healthcare.

A healthcare referral system is a structured method for guiding patients through different levels of care. It aims to ensure that patients receive the necessary care promptly and efficiently (WHO, 2019). Referral policies seek to optimise the use of healthcare resources. They also aim to reduce overcrowding in higher-level facilities and ensure patients receive appropriate care at the correct level (Bamgboye & Jarallah, 2018). In Nigeria, the National Health Policy details a three-tier referral system—primary, secondary, and tertiary care—each with specific roles and referral procedures (FMOH, 2016). Patients' knowledge and perceptions of the referral system significantly influence its effectiveness. Research indicates that a lack of awareness may lead patients to self-refer, thereby delaying access to appropriate care, increasing costs, and causing overcrowding in tertiary facilities (Onwujekwe et al., 2020; Agboola et al., 2022). In resource-limited settings like Nigeria, patients often avoid lower-level facilities due to perceptions of poor-quality care. They may also lack understanding of the referral rules or the benefits of adhering to proper referral procedures (Adewoyin & Ogunfowokan, 2019).

In Bayelsa State, tertiary hospitals still experience a high patient load. Reports show many arrive without being referred from lower-level facilities, indicating a possible misunderstanding of referral policies. To enhance services, optimise patient flow, and ensure adherence to national referral guidelines, it is crucial to identify gaps in patient knowledge. Assessing what patients understand can reveal areas where education and policy adjustments are necessary. Therefore, this study will evaluate what patients know and understand about referral system policies in federal and state tertiary healthcare facilities in Bayelsa State. The findings can then be used to recommend improvements in referral practices and the overall effectiveness of the health system.

Although referral guidelines are in place at both national and state levels, many patients in Bayelsa State still bypass primary and secondary care centres. They head straight to tertiary institutions without proper referral documents or understanding of the referral process (Olaoye et al., 2021). This behaviour strains tertiary healthcare providers, leading to long waits, overcrowding, inefficient use of resources, and delays in the management of serious cases (Agboola et al., 2022). Reports from FMC Yenagoa and NDUTH Okolobiri indicate that improper self-referrals remain common, highlighting a poor understanding of the referral system among patients. Past work in Nigeria has found that when patients lack knowledge of referral guidelines, the healthcare system suffers (Adewoyin & Ogunfowokan, 2019; Onwujekwe et al., 2020). Still, little work examines what patients in Bayelsa State know about referral policies. Without enough facts, decision-makers and hospital heads don't have what they need to create useful education and communication plans. The lack of data on what patients in Bayelsa State

know about referrals makes it difficult to improve the health system and ensure patients move smoothly through tertiary facilities. Therefore, this piece aims to fill this gap by assessing patients' understanding of referral system policies in federal and state tertiary hospitals in Bayelsa State.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in two hospitals in Bayelsa State: Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital (NDUTH), Okolobiri, established in 1973, and Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Yenagoa, established in 1957. NDUTH was upgraded in 2007 to a 158-bed tertiary hospital attached to Niger Delta University, while FMC is a federal tertiary facility with ongoing expansion. A descriptive cross-sectional survey assessed patients' knowledge of referral policies in these facilities. The target population comprised newly registered patients in the clinics of both hospitals, including GOPD, consultant clinics, and emergency units. Data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire titled "Patients' Knowledge and Awareness of Referral System Policies in Bayelsa State's Tertiary Hospitals," comprising demographic questions and Likert-scale items assessing perceptions of the referral system. Using Cochran's formula, a sample size of 276 was determined. Systematic sampling was used to select respondents, promoting representativeness. Data were gathered through on-site questionnaires, administered and collected immediately or rescheduled. Responses were checked for completeness and analysed in SPSS v21 using frequency and percentage analyses. Ethical approval was obtained from the hospital committees. Participants' confidentiality was assured, and consent was sought.

Results

Our findings showed that 53.6% of respondents (patients attending healthcare facilities) were female, 38.0% were aged 32-37 years, 36.6% had secondary-level education, and 31.5% were civil servants. A majority (63.4%) of respondents reported having no knowledge of the healthcare referral system. It was further revealed that 33.7% of respondents could not decide whether there is a structured laydown policy and guidelines for the healthcare referral system.

Research Question 1: Patients' Knowledge of Referral System Processes

Table 1: Showing Patients' Knowledge of Healthcare Referral System Processes

Patients' Knowledge of Referral System Processes	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I have no knowledge of the healthcare referral system	70 (25.7%)	99 (35.9%)	22 (8.0%)	46 (16.7%)	33 (12.0%)
I know that the referral system wastes patients' time and access to appropriate care	44 (15.9%)	96 (34.8%)	48 (17.4%)	71 (25.7%)	17 (6.2%)
The healthcare referral system is paramount in	70 (25.7%)	36	26	77	67

the healthcare system		(13.0%)	(9.4%)	(27.9%)	(24.3%)
The healthcare referral system does not ensure a close relationship between all levels of the healthcare system	70 (25.7%)	69 (25.0%)	46 (16.7%)	32 (11.6%)	59 (21.4%)
A healthcare referral system helps to increase transparency and reduce operational inefficiencies	41 (14.9%)	59 (21.4%)	29 (10.5%)	98 (33.5%)	49 (17.8%)
A healthcare referral system enhances existing processes for healthcare organisations in both large and small hospitals	49 (17.8%)	69 (25.0%)	74 (26.8%)	42 (15.2%)	42 (15.2%)

Source: field survey.

The results show that 99.76% of respondents, 35.9% and 27.5%, respectively, agree they have no knowledge of the healthcare referral system. Meanwhile, 46 respondents (16.7% and 12.0%) disagree, and 22 (8.0%) are undecided, indicating limited patient knowledge. Additionally, 96 respondents (34.8%) agree that the referral system wastes time and access; 71 (25.7%) strongly disagree; 48 (17.4%) are undecided; 44 (15.9%) strongly agree; and 17 (6.2%) strongly disagree. This reflects a lack of knowledge and experience with the system. Regarding its importance, 77 respondents (27.9%) disagree, 70 (25.4%) strongly agree, 67 (24.3%) strongly disagree, 36 (13.0%) agree, and 26 (9.4%) are undecided, showing divided opinions. On the relationship between healthcare levels, 70 (25.4%) agree, 69 (25.0%) strongly agree, 59 (21.4%) strongly disagree, 46 (16.7%) undecided, and 32 (11.6%) disagree. For transparency and efficiency, 98 (35.5%) disagree, 59 (21.4%) agree, 49 (17.8%) strongly disagree, 41 (14.9%) strongly agree, and 29 (10.5%) undecided, indicating mixed perceptions. Lastly, about process enhancement, 74 (26.8%) are undecided, 69 (25.0%) agree, 49 (17.8%) strongly agree, and 42 (15.2%) disagree, highlighting diverse views.

Research question 2: Patients' Awareness of Referral System Policies

Table 2: Showing Patients' Awareness of Referral System Policies

Patients' Awareness of Referral System Policies	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I am aware that there is a structured lay-down policy and guidelines on the healthcare referral system	55 (19.9%)	63 (22.8%)	93 (33.7%)	52 (18.8%)	13 (4.7%)
The healthcare referral system is not active in this facility	92 (33.3%)	61 (22.1%)	57 (20.7%)	43 (15.6%)	23 (8.3%)
A proper healthcare referral system cannot be effective in Bayelsa State	84 (30.4%)	138 (50.0%)	9 (3.3%)	24 (8.7%)	21 (7.6%)
I have faced some ugly situations in the healthcare referral system	30 (10.9%)	77 (27.9%)	24 (8.7%)	63 (22.8%)	82 (29.7%)

Source: field survey.

From the table, 33.7% of respondents could not decide if there is a structured healthcare referral policy. 22.8% agreed it exists, 19.9% strongly agreed, 18.8% disagreed, and 4.7% strongly disagreed. This indicates uncertainty about whether the policy is active. Regarding the system's activity, 33.3% strongly agreed it is inactive, 22.1% agreed, 20.7% were undecided, 15.6% disagreed, and 8.3% strongly disagreed. The majority (50.0%) believed that a proper referral system isn't effective in Bayelsa, with 30.4% strongly agreeing. Disbelief about encountering problematic situations in healthcare referral was also notable, with 29.7% strongly disagreeing, 27.9% agreeing, and 22.8% disagreeing.

Discussions of findings

The study was carried out at two tertiary healthcare facilities in Bayelsa State: Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, and Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa. More participants responded from the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa. Concerning demographic characteristics, female patients outnumbered male patients at both facilities. In terms of age, most respondents (patients) were between 32 and 37 years old. Additionally, most patients had attained a secondary level of education. Furthermore, most respondents were civil servants.

The findings revealed that the majority (63.4%) of respondents lacked knowledge of the healthcare referral system. It was also found that slightly more than half (50.7%) of respondents agreed that the referral system wastes patients' time and hinders access to appropriate care. This may be due to most respondents not being familiar with the healthcare referral system. Additionally, the majority (52.2%) of respondents disagreed that the healthcare referral system is essential in the healthcare system.

It was found that, according to respondents, more than half (50.7%) of patients indicated that the healthcare referral system does not ensure a close relationship across all levels of the healthcare system. It was also found that a slightly above-average (51.3%) of the respondents disagreed that the healthcare referral system helps increase transparency and reduce operational inefficiencies. Furthermore, it was found that (26.8%) of the respondents were neutral (undecided) about whether the healthcare referral system enhances existing processes for healthcare organisations, both large and small hospitals.

The study found that 33.7% of respondents could not determine whether a structured lay-down policy and guidelines for the healthcare referral system exist. This indicates that many respondents are unaware of the activity level of the referral policies and guidelines, if any. Additionally, 55.4% of participants agreed that the healthcare referral system is inactive in their facility. Moreover, 80.4% believe that an effective healthcare referral system cannot be achieved in Bayelsa State, possibly due to its geographical location and terrain. Interestingly, 52.5% of respondents reported not facing challenging situations related to the healthcare referral process.

Conclusions

The findings clearly show that patients have very limited knowledge of the healthcare referral system, raising serious concerns about their ability to navigate it effectively. Moreover, patients are largely unaware of the comprehensive policies and detailed guidelines that govern and shape the referral process. Additionally, the current healthcare referral system is inadequate in encouraging strong, collaborative, and well-coordinated relationships across all levels of the healthcare network, highlighting a critical area that urgently needs targeted improvements and reforms.

Recommendations

1. Patients as well as the general public should be given an enlightenment on the healthcare referral system.
2. The government should provide adequate healthcare facilities for patients to have access to at all levels of care
3. Policies and guidelines of the healthcare referral system should be provided.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was declared.

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